

Time as a Result of the Computational Complexity of the Measurements of Multiple Eigenstates

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What is Time?

It is often thought that time is the axis responsible for the change of information. According to this definition, in the absence of time, there would be no “axis” for information to change and all information present in the universe would be static and unchanging. Per this model, the absence of time would indicate an absence of change and a “frozen” existence where every entity is always only in just one single state of itself. I would however argue just the opposite - that in the absence of time, it is not that every entity is in one state of itself but rather in an infinite amount of states of itself simultaneously. Time therefore is not what causes frozen entities to “change” but rather what causes ever changing entities to slow down or stop. In my view time is not the added dimension that allows entities to “change” but rather a divider that narrows infinite dimensional information into separate “segments” of information each that are finitely dimensional. Each of these segments of informational entities would be translated as those informational entities having separated finite states at different “moments” in time. Instead of them having an infinite amount of eigenstates at once, they would have a divided number of singular eigenstates separated across different moments.

The Relationship Between and Velocity

Support for this model can be shown through the relationship between time and velocity. If the velocity of an object is equal to its change in distance over its change in time then this would imply that when there is 0 change in time (which is what would result if there was an absence of time), it's velocity could not be 0. This is because any number divided by 0 could not possibly equal 0. In fact for any finite numerator, any denominator of 0 would result in a solution tending to infinity.

This would mean that in the absence of time, since there would still be changes in an entities state that exist, any velocity would not be equal to 0 but rather tend to infinity. This shows how in the absence of time, entities are actually infinitely changing rather than not static. Static entities on the other hand would require an “infinite change in time” to be truly static. This shows how there is an inverse relationship between velocity and the magnitude of time for the number of eigenstates of an entity.

See the case of an entity approaching infinite speed. When an entity approaches infinite speed it is capable of traversing point a to point b in the same moment since 0 time would pass. This is because any time there is infinite speed, there must be 0 time that passes between the entities source and destination point. Moreover, if an entity is capable of traversing the distance between point a and point b in 0 time this would mean that ultimately it could also traverse

point b to point c within the same moment. Transitively, an entity could essentially traverse any amount of distances within the same moment if it in fact has infinite velocity and therefore could be “anywhere at once”. While this example applies to location specifically, location itself is just an informational degree of freedom like particle charge or particle spin and can be extended to any other degree of freedom for any entity. Therefore for any entity traveling at infinite speed (or changing its states at infinite speed) there could be no time present for it and it would have to be “in every possible state of its degree of freedom” at once. Only once time is introduced can these entities states be divided into different states at different times. This shows that objectively, the slowing of entities changing states is in fact what causes the need for time to be present and not the other way around.

Subjective Observers and the Computation of Information

Now the reason that subjective observers experience a sense of passing time is simply because they are incapable of making sense of informational entities that are in an infinite amount of states of themselves at once. Since brains are measuring devices and therefore can by definition only measure one state of one informational degree of freedom at a time, they essentially force infinitely changing entities to narrow into one state of themselves in order to be measured by the brain. Objectively these entities would still always be in an infinite amount of states of themselves simultaneously. However from the perspective of an observer these entities can only be in one state of themselves at once since that is how the brain works; it can only measure a degree of freedom as being in a single state. This forces the entities to be viewed across multiple separate “times” from the viewpoint of subjective observers since again measurement is only effective when an entity is in one state at one time. After all measurement itself is the concept of detecting a single state of an infinitely changing entity. The brain could not measure multiple states of a degree of freedom at once so divides them into seeming to happen at different times. Time in this way from the viewpoint of an observer is analogous to measurement complexity.

This is essentially what causes the “measurement problem” in quantum mechanics. The reason that the wave function of possible states of a particle seems to narrow infinitely into one state upon measurement by an observer or by a measuring device is because the measurement of the entity can detect just one single state of the many amount of eigenstates for the particle (which itself is just an informational degree of freedom). Once the entity is measured by the observer from the perspective of the observers brain it must be in one state of itself or else it could not be measured. Therefore it seems to “collapse” upon measurement by the device since the device can only make sense of a single of its states at one time.

However, if this is true wouldn't the resulting state of collapsed entities be random? Why do they “collapse” in accordance with the probabilistic schrodingers equation? The reason is because the measured states of the particle must “fit” in with the informational world of the observer. This can be likened to how a new piece of a puzzle must fit in with the existing pieces of the puzzle in order to make the entire puzzle cohesive and whole. In order for the

brain to measure these entities in a way that makes sense to the observer, they must subjectively collapse in a manner that fits in geometrically into the informational world of the observer. This also explains the phenomenon of quantum entanglement. The reason that the measurement of entities at a distance can affect the measured states of one another is because geometrically it is possible for information to be dependent on other information even if the information is not immediately in proximity to one other. For example in the case of a chess match, a move at one square can consequently affect the designation of pieces far apart from it. This shows that it is not mere proximity that determines the measured states of entities but rather their informational dependencies and contingencies. If informationally one collapsed state of a particle is dependent on another, then it must then collapse that way to fit cohesively into the larger informational world of the measuring device.

At this point it could be asked why then do multiple observers measure a particle as being in the same eigenstate? Wouldn't particles only be measured a certain way to the observer if this were the case and not other observers as well? The answer I would give is that though observers each have their own individual informational worlds that are a result of their brains measurements of entities, they are also all part of a shared larger informational world. This means that if one observer measures an entity as being in a certain state then any other observer who has information dependent on the information of the first observer would also need to measure that particle to be in the same state in order for it to be consistent with their own informational world. In this way it can be seen how the informational worlds of different observers being dependent on one another causes the observers to measure entities as being in the same state since that agreed upon measurement is needed for the cohesiveness of the shared informational world in which they both inhabit.

This shared informational world can also explain the constant measurement for the speed of light amongst different observers. The universe is essentially itself an informational world that contains a limited amount of information. This means that instead of information within the universe being in infinite states of itself by default the universe is itself a "subjective view" of an observer. This can be likened to the universe being a closed box within an infinitely opened space. Within the closed box there must exist finiteness relating to the total size of the box.

The total size of the box would be the number of informational states and degrees of freedom that can be present within it or the computational complexity of the boxes information.

This means time itself exists since the universe is not all that exists objectively. The universe in its entirety is rather a single "component" of the infinite whole or "parental hilbert space" and therefore has entities within it that don't exist in infinite states of themselves at once since time is present within it. Time is present within it specifically because it is already a subjective division of the objective whole and not the objective whole itself. Since it is therefore not capable of containing an infinite amount of entities at once it must narrow those entities into being at a finite amount of states at a finite amount of times. This is consistent with the constant speed of light since the speed of light is essentially related to the informational complexity of the universe. If the universe itself was the objective whole then the maximum informational

propagation speed would be infinite, however because the universe itself is a subjective division of information within the infinite whole, the speed of information within it must not be infinite but rather be related to the total complexity of information that is within the whole subjective division that is the universe.

The Past and Future

This model can also explain why observers experience a separate past and future. The past is simply information that is “set” in their informational world or 100% defined. This would simply be measured information that is in only a single state of itself. Future information would be information that is unmeasured and in multiple states of itself but can still be imagined since it probabilistically can collapse into different states that are dependent upon the configurations of the entities within their informational worlds. In reality there is no “time” but only a present. The probabilistic nature of entities both measured and unmeasured is what causes the brain to experience subjective “divisions” in the compilations of states of particles it then ends up defining as the “past” and the “future”.

The Quantum Zeno Effect

The quantum Zeno effect is also in line with this definition of time. According to the Zeno effect, entities that are measured more often “change” their states less versus those that are measured less. This means that the very act of increased measurement essentially causes the states of entity to narrow increasingly across a duration of time. Continued measurement would therefore cause the informational world that these entities inhabit to become less and less changing which results in less of a perception of change from the perspective of the observer since less informational states are being present within their measurements which need to be divided by the brain in order to be made sense of. In this way the experience of time relative to change is merely a result of the computational complexity of an observers informational world.

An informational world that has less dependencies results in less informational configurations which then result in sparser divisions of time from the perspective of the observer. This is why infinitely measured entities do not change - because their informational worlds have no divided informational contingencies within it that need to be separated into different times from the perspective of the observer.